

ULTRASOUND SIGNS OF CAROTID ATHEROSCLEROSIS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF EARLY CEREBRAL CIRCULATORY DISORDERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10253741>

Annotation. Atherosclerosis occupies one of the first places among the risk factors of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular disease. Vascular diseases of the brain are the most important medical and social problem due to their high prevalence and severe consequences for the health of the population. In Europe, around 1.5 million people are predicted to have severe carotid vascular stenosis by 2025. Atherosclerotic injury of the carotid artery (ka) occupies a leading position in the development of tserebrovascular diseases.

keywords: ultrasound diagnostics, carotid, stroke, occurrence

The aim of the study was to study the association between changes in neurological status and the presence of atherosclerotic lesions in the carotid arteries.

Materials and methods of research. The study was conducted on the basis of the Bukhara branch of the RNCMP. The study involved 175 people (85 men and 90 women) aged 44 to 75 years (average age 63.8 ± 7.1), in whom subclinical manifestations of carotid artery atherosclerosis were determined according to ultrasound data. Neurological status was assessed, blood lipid parameters (total cholesterol, high and low density lipoproteins, triglycerides) were determined. Ultrasound scanning of the carotid arteries assessed the presence of atherosclerotic plaques according to a 4-point system (0 — absence of elevated atherosclerotic lesions, 1-2 — stable atherosclerotic plaques with stenosis of the lumen of the vessel up to 20% and from 20 to 70%, respectively, 3 — hemodynamically significant atherosclerotic plaques with stenosis of more than 70% of the lumen of the carotid arteries), and The thickness of the intima-media complex of the common carotid artery was also measured on a distal segment with a length of 1 cm in three projections. The study was carried out on the SSI-5000 device (Sonoscape, China). When assessing neurological symptoms, subjective complaints of study participants about headaches, dizziness, insomnia and mnesic disorders, and increased fatigue were taken into account. In addition, the function of the cranial nerves, indicators of coordination and statics, changes in the sensory and motor spheres, and the pyramidal system were determined.

Results and discussion. The thickness of the IC of the carotid arteries in men was significantly higher than in women ($p < 0.001$). In men, the analysis of the relationship of the integral indicator of neurological status with direct quantitative characteristics of carotid atherosclerosis revealed a correlation with the average and maximum thickness of the intimo-medial layer of the carotid arteries ($r = 0.291$, $p = 0.008$ and $r = 0.254$, $p = 0.021$, respectively), but not with the presence of atherosclerotic plaques in the carotid artery basin ($p = 0.47$). The average and maximum thickness of the carotid artery IC correlated with each other in both men and women ($r = 0.963$ and $r = 0.975$, respectively, $p < 0.001$). The maximum thickness of the IC correlated with the severity of atherosclerotic plaques in both men and women ($r = 0.230$, $p = 0.036$ and $r = 0.295$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). The average thickness of the IC correlated with the severity of ASB in women ($r = 0.283$, $p = 0.001$), and in men this relationship did not reach the level of statistical significance ($p = 0.06$).

Conclusions.

1. Diffuse thickening of the intimo-medial layer of the carotid arteries is one of the risk factors determining even minimally pronounced, subclinical changes in neurological status at the earliest stages of the formation of cerebrovascular pathology.

2. Ultrasound imaging of the main arteries supplying blood to the brain, with determination of the thickness of the intimo-medial layer of the carotid arteries, can become one of the priority methods for diagnosing atherosclerotic lesions with an early assessment of the prognostic risk of developing cardiovascular and cerebrovascular complications of an ischemic nature.

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